

Incomplete Dissociation of Salts*

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Arrhenius advanced the theory of Ionic Dissociation in 1887. Based on this theory, Ostwald put forward his Dilution Law in 1888. In the case of uniunivalent electrolyte the law may be expressed as ;

$$K = \frac{\alpha^2 C}{1 - \alpha}$$

Ostwald's Dilution Law as is well known, is obeyed by a large number of acids and bases. It does not generally work well with salts. At one time it was thought that it would work even with salts like potassium chloride and very dilute solutions of KCl, say of the order of 10^{-5} moles/litre, seemed to obey Ostwald's Dilution Law.

Bousfield's¹ measurements of the conduction of potassium chloride at 18° seemed to support this view as may be evident from the following figures :

$C \times 10^5$	0.0	2.0	4.0	6.0	8.0	10.0
K	0.020 ± 0.001	0.02002	0.02006	0.02022	0.02050	0.02102

At slightly higher concentrations Ostwald's Dilution Law fails completely in case of KCl solution.

In case of strong electrolytes it is found that equivalent conductance plotted against square root of concentration at low concentrations gives a straight line. This is known as Kohlrausch's Law. This law breaks down completely in case of weak electrolytes.

The applicability of Kohlrausch's law and the additivity of ionic conductances even at finite concentrations and the failure of Ostwald's Dilution Law in the case of strong electrolytes even at moderate concentration, say of the order of 10^{-3} gm. equivalent/litre paved the way to the idea of complete dissociation in the case of strong electrolyte.

Attempts began to be made to explain the decrease in conductance due to interionic forces. Hertz² seems to have been the first to formulate a plausible picture in terms of interionic attraction. J. C. Ghosh³ was the next to attempt a picture of conductance based on incomplete disorder. Milner⁴ successfully analysed the problem. The mathematical

*The twentieth Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray Memorial Lecture delivered at the Saha Institute of Nuclear Physics, Calcutta on January 15, 1968.

1. W. R. Bousfield, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, **103**, 307.

2. P. Hertz, *Ann. Physik.*, 1912, **37**, 4.

3. J. C. Ghosh, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, **113**, 449, 627, 707, 790; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1919, **15**, 154.

4. R. Milner, *Phil. Mag.*, 1912, **23**, 551; 1913, **25**, 742.

treatment given by him was complicated and did not give a simple formula which could be used by those who did not follow his mathematics. The concept of 'ionic atmosphere' was introduced by Debye. Debye and Hückel⁵ successfully solved the problem of limiting law for the activity coefficient. Onsager⁶ a little later developed a general treatment of the motion of ions in solution in an electric atmosphere and derived the limiting law for equivalent conductance in case of complete dissociation.

Onsager's theory for equivalent conductance in the case of uniunivalent completely dissociated electrolyte results in the following equation :—

$$\Lambda = \frac{K \times 1000}{C} = \Lambda_0 - \left[\frac{82.4}{(DT)^{\frac{1}{2}} \eta} + \frac{8.20 \times 10^5}{(DT)^{3/2}} \Lambda_0 \right] \sqrt{C}$$

where K is the specific conductance, C is the concentration in gram molecules per litre and Λ , Λ_0 , D, T and η have their usual significance.

The above equation justifies the plot of equivalent conductance against \sqrt{C} being a straight line. While this equation works magnificently well, in case of uniunivalent electrolytes, similar equations for biunivalent, unibivalent and bibivalent electrolytes do not work well. In case of unibivalent and biunivalent electrolytes it does not seem to be certain whether the failure is due to incomplete dissociation.

If there is incomplete dissociation then the concentration of the ionised electrolyte becomes αC , hence Onsager's equation reduced to the form :

$$\frac{k \times 1000}{\alpha C} = \Lambda_0 - \left[\frac{82.4}{(DT)^{\frac{1}{2}} \eta} + \frac{8.20 \times 10^5}{(DT)^{3/2}} \Lambda_0 \right] \sqrt{C}$$

for a uniunivalent electrolyte.

This picture has worked very well in case of weak electrolytes, and has given very good values of dissociation constants. Davies⁷ has used this picture to calculate the dissociation constants of a large number of so called strong electrolytes. He has generally obtained the degree of dissociation by this method and has relied on getting the value of activity coefficient from freezing point data or empirical equations⁹ or from Debye Hückel equation.

When equivalent conductance at infinite dilution is known by indirect methods the above equation gives value of ' α ' in a few approximations. If Λ_0 is not known a more cumbersome method of approximation involving dissociation constant itself has to be used. An account of this is given in the Physical Chemistry of Electrolyte Solutions by Harned and Owen.

5. P. Debye and E. Hückel, *Zeit. Physik.*, 1923, **24**, 185.

6. L. Onsager, *Zeit. Physik.*, 1927, **28**, 277.

7. C. W. Davies, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1927, **23**, 351.

8. E. C. Righellato, and C. W. Davies, *Ibid.*, 1930, **26**, 592.

9. C.W. Davies, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **140**, 277.

The following table gives the value of K as found by conductance method :

	K	Ref	$K \times 10^4$	Ref.
KClO ₃	... 1.4	7		
KNO ₃	... 1.4	7		
AgNO ₃	... 1.21	7		
TiNO ₃	... 0.52	7	MgSO ₄ ... 78	11
TiCl	... 0.300	7	CaSO ₄ ... 53	12
(CdNO ₃) ⁺	... 0.394	8	CuSO ₄ ... 50	11
(CdCl) ⁺	... 0.0101	8	ZnSO ₄ ... 53	11
(PbNO ₃) ⁺	... 0.0647	8	CdSO ₄ ... 49	11
(PbCl) ⁺	... 0.0304	8	MgSO ₄ ... 63*	12
(CaNO ₃) ⁺	... 0.521	8	CoSO ₄ ... 34*	12
(SrNO ₃) ⁺	... 0.150	8	NiSO ₄ ... 40*	12
(BaNO ₃) ⁺	... 0.121	8	CuSO ₄ ... 43*	13
(LiSO ₄) ⁻	... 0.229	8	ZnSO ₄ ... 49*	13
(NaSO ₄) ⁻	... 0.198	8	Cu Malonate 0.025	13
(KSO ₄) ⁻	... 0.151	8	Zn Malonate 2.1*	12
(AgSO ₄) ⁻	... 0.05	8	Cd Malonate 5.1*	12
(TiSO ₄) ⁻	... 0.0472	8	[KFe (CN) ₆] 55*	14
CaAC ⁺	... 1.00*	9	Mg SO ₄ ... 131**	15
(CaOH) ⁺	... 0.031*	10	ZnSO ₄ ... 107**	16
(BaOH) ⁺	... 0.23*	10		

* estimated at 25°, **at 35° and the rest at 18°.

Except in the case of uniunivalent electrolytes the dissociation constants seem to be correct.

We thought of approaching the problem from the e.m.f. side. I am omitting discussion of Debye Hückel theory and activity coefficient as they are well known. We made certain assumptions and these are :

(1) that KCl is completely dissociated in aqueous solution;

(2) that the activity coefficient of K⁺ and Cl⁻ ions in KCl solutions are equal to each other and so equal to the mean activity coefficient of KCl;

(3) that the activity coefficient of an ion depends on its ionic strength only;

(4) that the activity coefficient of K⁺ in KNO₃ solutions is the same as the activity coefficient of K⁺ in KCl solutions of the same ionic strength. From this activity coefficient of NO₃⁻ at various ionic strengths has been calculated;

(5) that the activity coefficient of NO₃⁻ ions in Ba(NO₃)₂ or Pb(NO₃)₂ solutions is the same as that of NO₃⁻ ions in KNO₃ solutions of the same ionic strength. From this activity coefficient of Pb⁺⁺ and Ba⁺⁺ ions at various ionic strengths have been calculated. The activity coefficient of Ba⁺⁺ can also be calculated from the activity coefficient of

10. C. W. Davies, *J. Chem. Soc., Ibid.*, 1939, **141**, 349.

11. ,, ,, *Ibid.*, 1938, **140**, 2093.

12. R. W. Money and C. W. Davies, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1932, **28**, 609.

13. B. B. Owen and R. W. Gurry, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 3074.

14. C. W. Davies, *Ibid.*, 1937, **59**, 1760.

15. P. B. Das, P. K. Das and D. Patnaik, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **36**, 410.

16. S. Devi and P. B. Das, *Indian Jour. of Applied Chem.*, 1963, **26**, 152.

BaCl₂ and KCl in solution. We have assumed that lead nitrate, barium nitrate and barium chloride are completely dissociated;

(6) that the activity coefficient of any bivalent positive ion which can not be measured may be taken to be the same as that of the Ba⁺⁺ ion at the same ionic strength in dilute solutions;

(7) that the activity coefficient of K⁺ in K₂SO₄ solutions is the same as that of K⁺ ion in KCl solutions of the same ionic strength. The activity coefficient of SO₄⁼ ion at various ionic strengths is thus calculated from the knowledge of activity coefficients of K₂SO₄ and KCl;

(8) that the activity coefficient of acetate ion is the same as that of chloride ion at the same ionic strength;

(9) that the activity coefficient at low concentrations used by us can be taken to be the same as the activity coefficient at that molality;

(10) that liquid junction potential is eliminated by KCl and NH₄NO₃ bridges.

With these assumptions it becomes possible to calculate the activity coefficient of various ions at different ionic strengths. Whether the calculated value of activity coefficients are fairly correct or not were tested with the data of e.m.f. of the cell; Cd_xHg_y | CdCl₂ AgCl | Ag, at 35° measured by Harned and Fitzgerald¹⁷.

m	0.001	0.002	0.005	0.007	0.010
E	0.83457	0.81098	0.78176	0.77170	0.76122

The e.m.f. of the cell at 35° is given by $E = 0.56955 - \frac{RT}{2F} \log_e a_{Cd^{++}} \times a_{Cl^-}$

Hence for any concentration (molality) used in the cell, $a_{Cd^{2+}} \times a_{Cl^-}$ is found out from the e.m.f. measurements. For any value of m, an arbitrary value is assigned to the molality of Cd²⁺. This gives a corresponding value of the molalities of CdCl⁺ and Cl⁻, because

$$[Cd]_{total} = [CdCl^+] + [Cd^{2+}], [Cl]_{total} = [CdCl^+] + [Cl^-] = 2 [Cd]_T$$

$$\text{Now } \mu = 2 [Cd^{2+}] + \frac{1}{2} [CdCl^+] + \frac{1}{2} [Cl^-].$$

Knowing μ we can find out the activity coefficient of Cd²⁺ i.e. (f^{2+}), CdCl⁺ (f^+ taken to be that of K⁺) and Cl⁻ ions (f^-) at the ionic strengths concerned. From this we can calculate the $[Cd^{2+}] \times [Cl^-]^2 \times f^{2+} \times f^-$. If this differs from $a_{Cd^{2+}} \times a_{Cl^-}^2$ calculated from

$E = 0.56955 - \frac{RT}{2F} \log_e a_{Cd^{++}} \times a_{Cl^-}$ then the molality value of Cd²⁺ is altered by successive approximations till the two agree. Since $[Cd^{2+}]$, $[CdCl^+]$, f^+ , $[Cl^-]$ and f_- are known we can calculate the value of

$$K = \frac{[Cd^{2+}] \times [Cl^-] \times f^{2+} \times f^-}{[CdCl^+] \times f_{CdCl^+}} = \frac{[Cd^{2+}] \times [Cl^-] f^{2+}}{[CdCl^+]}$$

The value of K calculated for the various molalities from the data of Harned and Fitzgerald is given below :

[CdCl ₂] _x	0.001	0.002	0.005	0.007	0.01	Mean
K × 10 ³	9.70	9.00	10.00	9.93	9.98	9.72

Molality has been indicated by [] in the above paragraph.

It may also be seen that value obtained for the above Dissociation Constant by Davies⁸ from conductivity data comes to 10.1 × 10⁻³. We were thus encouraged to calculate activity coefficient of individual ions at various ionic strengths for using them in the study of equilibria.

We measured the e.m.f. of the cell :

Then the e.m.f. of the cell will be given by

$$E = \frac{RT}{2F} \log_e \frac{Cf'^{2+}}{\alpha C f^{2+}} = \frac{RT}{2F} \log_e \frac{f'^{2+}}{\alpha f^{2+}}$$

Where f'^{2+} indicates the activity coefficient of Pb^{2+} in lead nitrate solutions, f^{2+} the activity coefficient of Pb^{2+} in lead acetate solutions and α the degree of dissociation of Pb Ac^+ . The value of f'^{2+} is calculated from the values of activity coefficients of $\text{Pb (NO}_3)_2$, KNO_3 and KCl at the same ionic strength. A rough value of α is found to begin with by assuming $f'^{2+} = f^{2+}$. From this a very approximate value of μ is found and fresh value of f^{2+} is found. The process is repeated till the value α and f^{2+} do not change any more. In this way we get the value of α .

$$\text{Now } K = \frac{\alpha C f'^{2+} X C (1 + \alpha) f_{\text{Ac}^-}}{C (1 - \alpha) f_{\text{PbAc}^+}}$$

The value of $\alpha C f'^{2+}$ is known directly from the e.m.f. of the cell.

$$\text{Hence } \log K = \log \alpha C f'^{2+} + \log \frac{1 + \alpha}{1 - \alpha} + \log f_{\text{Ac}^-} - \log f_{\text{PbAc}^+}$$

$$\text{Since } \log f = -AZ^2 \sqrt{\bar{\mu}} + B\mu$$

So the above expression reduces itself to ;

$$\log \alpha C f'^{2+} + \log \frac{1 + \alpha}{1 - \alpha} = \log K + \beta \mu$$

If left hand expression is plotted against μ , we get value of K . The value of K obtained¹⁸ is 3.1×10^{-3} . The next cell to be studied by us was

then the e.m.f. of the above cell would be given by the equation

$$E = \frac{RT}{F} \log_e \frac{2f'_{\text{Ac}^-}(\text{activity coefficient of Ac}^- \text{ in NaAc})}{(1 + \alpha)f_{\text{Ac}^-}(\text{activity of the Ac}^- \text{ in PbAc}_2)}$$

On calculating, as in previous case, α comes out to be negative, which means that our scheme of dissociation is not correct. The scheme which is satisfactory is

With this scheme the e.m.f. of the two cells

are given by $E_1 = \frac{RT}{2F} \log_e \frac{f'^{2+}}{\alpha\beta f'^{2+}}$

$$E_2 = \frac{RT}{F} \log_e \frac{2f'_{\text{Ac}^-}}{\beta(1 + \alpha)f_{\text{Ac}^-}}$$

It is possible to solve these equations by the method of approximations by using assumptions about activity coefficient given earlier and to calculate the value of K_1 and K_2

$$\text{where } K_1 = \frac{\alpha_{\text{PbAc}^+} \times \alpha_{\text{Ac}^-}}{(\text{PbAc}_2)} \text{ and } K_2 = \frac{\alpha_{\text{Pb}^{2+}} \times \alpha_{\text{Ac}^-}}{\alpha_{\text{PbAc}^+}}$$

which come out to be 3.0×10^{-2} and 3.89×10^{-3} respectively.

These¹⁹ results have been confirmed by the study of the cells of the type $\text{Hg}_y \text{Pb}_x \mid \text{PbAc}_2 \text{Hg}_2 \text{Ac}_2 \mid \text{Hg}$ where there is no liquid junction potential.

18. N. K. Das, S. Aditya and B. Prasad, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **29**, 169.

19. S. Aditya, and B. Prasad, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **30**, 213.

The dissociation constant corresponding to $\text{MAc}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{M}^{++} + \text{Ac}^-$ have also been measured in the case of cadmium, mercury, copper, nickel, cobalt and zinc salts by setting suitable cells and some other methods. Quite a number of the cells have liquid junction potential. The following table gives the data : .

MAc ⁺	Pb ¹⁹	Zn ²⁰	Cu ²¹	Ni ²²	Co ²³	Cd ²⁴
K × 10 ³	3.89	30.0	4.00	74.1	43.5	17.0

The dissociation of mercury acetate has been measured by solubility method. It is found that HgAc_2^{25} is mostly undissociated. The $K_1K_2 = 3.7 \times 10^{-9}$.

Our next attempt was to measure the dissociation constants of the salts of the type MSO_4 . We studied cadmium, zinc, copper, beryllium, magnesium, manganese, nickel and cobalt sulphates. The paper on cadmium sulphate²⁶ has already been published and Zinc sulphate is under publication. The result of other sulphates will be published soon.

In case of cadmium sulphate we studied the following type of cells ;

- (a) $\text{Hg}_y \text{ Cd}_x \mid \text{CdSO}_4 \parallel \text{s.b.} \parallel \text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \mid \text{Cd}_x \text{ Hg}_y$
(c)
- (b) $\text{Hg} \mid \text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4 \text{ K}_2\text{SO}_4 \parallel \text{s.b.} \parallel \text{CdSO}_4 \text{ Hg}_2 \text{ SO}_4 \mid \text{Hg}$
(e)
- (c) $\text{H}_y \text{ Cd}_x \mid \text{CdSO}_4 \text{ Hg}_2 \text{ SO}_4 \mid \text{Hg}$
(e)
- (d) $\text{Hg}_y \text{ Cd}_x \mid \text{K}_2\text{SO}_4 \text{ CdSO}_4 \parallel \text{s.b.} \parallel \text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \mid \text{Cd}_x \text{ Hg}_y$
(C₁) (C₂) (C₂)
- (e) $\text{Hg} \mid \text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4 \text{ K}_2\text{SO}_4 \parallel \text{s.b.} \parallel \text{K}_2\text{SO}_4 \text{ CdSO}_4 \text{ Hg}_2\text{SO}_4 \mid \text{Hg}$
(C₁+C₂) (C₁) (C₂)
- (f) $\text{Hg}_y \text{ Cd}_x \mid \text{K}_2\text{SO}_4 \text{ CdSO}_4 \text{ Hg}_2\text{SO}_4 \mid \text{Hg}$
(C₁) (C₂)

We made the same assumption about liquid junction potential and activity coefficients as in the case of acetates. We thought that $\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2-}$ is also formed to a small extent but that seems to be wrong. From each of the above cells it is possible to find a value of 'K'. The most reliable value given below should be obtained with cell 'c'. In cell 'f' the ionic strength becomes much higher. Unlike in the case of $\text{CdCl}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Cd}^{2+} + \text{Cl}^-$, the value of K goes on changing with concentration in case of cell 'c' and other cells.

[CdSO ₄] Total	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.08	0.09	0.10
K × 10 ³	5.47	4.10	3.37	3.18	3.07	2.84	2.72	2.61

20. S. Bardhan and S. Aditya, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **32**, 105.

21. S. C. Sircar, S. Aditya and B. Prasad, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **30**, 633.

22. P. K. Jena, S. Aditya and B. Prasad, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **30**, 736.

23. S. Bardhan, and S. Aditya, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **32**, 109.

24. S. Aditya, and B. Prasad, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **30**, 255.

25. P. Mohapatra, S. Aditya and B. Prasad, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **30**, 509.

26. P. K. Jena and B. Prasad, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **39**, 33.

This may be due to our assumption not being absolutely valid at these concentrations but they are bound to be valid at $\mu = 0$. Hence the value of K was plotted against \sqrt{C} to get the thermodynamic value of K and it came out to be 7.7×10^{-3} .

In case of zinc sulphate with the cell of the type 'c' the following value of K were obtained.

$[\text{ZnSO}_4]_{\text{T}}$	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.08	0.09
$K \times 10^3$	6.82	5.59	4.94	4.74	4.39	4.17	4.03	3.89

The value of K obtained by plotting K against \sqrt{C} and extrapolating to $C=0$ comes to 7.5×10^{-3} .

The dissociation²⁷ of MgSO_4 , CuSO_4 , ZnSO_4 , BeSO_4 , MnSO_4 , CoSO_4 and NiSO_4 were also studied with the cell of the type 'b' in cadmium sulphate studied both with KCl bridge and NH_4NO_3 bridge. Ammonium nitrate bridge was found to be not so reliable. Values of ' K ' obtained with KCl bridge for each concentration was plotted against \sqrt{C} in case of each of the salts and a straight line was obtained in case of beryllium, copper, nickel and cobalt sulphates. In case of magnesium sulphate there seemed to be complete dissociation up to 0.03. The plot is not reliable. In case of manganese sulphate the curve goes up and down. The following table gives the extrapolated values of K in case of beryllium, copper, nickel and cobalt salts and mean values in case of magnesium and manganese salts.

Metal	Be	Cu	Ni	Co	Mg	Mn
$K \times 10^3$	6.7	6.8	9.0	11.7	10.82	5.33

Davies, Monk, Evans²⁸; Nair and Nancollas²⁹ have used the cell of the type

to study the dissociation of MSO_4 or the formation of ion pairs $\text{M}^{++} + \text{SO}_4^{--} \rightleftharpoons \text{MSO}_4$. They have eliminated liquid junction potential. In many cases M^{++} and Cl^- ions also interact. The results of the authors are vitiated by the formation of MCl^+ not having been taken into account. Their values of K are however much more concordant than our values but the values obtained are of the same order as in our case. Some of their figures at 35° are given below :

MSO_4	Mg	Zn	Mn	Co	Ni
$K \times 10^3$	4.03	4.72	5.53	3.96	4.05

We have measured the dissociation constant of CdCl^{+30} .

First of all we studied the cell ;

The e.m.f. of this cell is given by

$$E = E_0 + \frac{RT}{F} \log_e a_{\text{H}^+} \times a_{\text{Cl}^-}$$

27. S. C. Sircar, P. K. Jena, and B. Prasad, Unpublished work.

28. Jones and Monk, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1952, **48**, 929.

29. V. S. K. Nair and G. H. Nancollas, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 3708; 1959, 3934.

30. G. Sahu and B. Prasad, Unpublished work.

$$= E_o + \frac{RT}{F} \log_e [H^+] \times [Cl^-] + \frac{RT}{F} \times 2.303 \log f^+ f^-$$

$$= E_o + \frac{RT}{F} \log_e [H^+] \times [Cl^-] - \frac{RT}{F} \times 2.303 \left(\frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - B\mu \right)$$

or $E - \frac{RT}{F} \log_e [H^+] \times [Cl^-] + \frac{2RT}{F} \times 2.303 \frac{A\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} = E_o + \frac{RT}{F} \times 2.303 \times B\mu$

By plotting L.H.S. against μ a straight line is obtained, the slope of which gives the value of B. So we can find $f^+ f^-$ or f^+ . The values of f^+ found by this method are in good agreement with those found by Harned and his associates.

Next we studied cell ;

The e.m.f. of this cell is given by the same equation as that for the previous one for

$E = E_o + \frac{RT}{F} \log_e [H^+] \times [Cl^-] f^+ f^-$. An arbitrary value is given to ionic strength. The corresponding value of $f^+ f^-$ is calculated from the equation $-\log f^+ f^- = \frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - B\mu$.

Since the value of $[H^+]$ is known a rough value of $[Cl^-]$ is found.

Now $[Cl]_T = [Cl^-] + [CdCl^+]$ and $[Cd]_T = [Cd^{++}] + [CdCl^+]$

Since $[Cl]_T$ is known and a rough value of $[Cl^-]$ has been found, a rough value of $[CdCl^+]$ and $[Cd^{++}]$ are found. Now a new value of ionic strength is calculated from ;

$$\mu = \frac{1}{2} [H^+] + \frac{1}{2} [Cl^-] + \frac{1}{2} [CdCl^+] + 2 [Cd^{++}]$$

With this new value of μ , a new value of $f_+ f_-$ is found and the process is repeated till there is no appreciable change in μ . For every HCl and CdCl₂ mixture we know μ , $[Cd^{++}]$, $[Cl^-]$ and $[CdCl^+]$

Now $K = \frac{[Cd^{++}] [Cl^-] f_+ f_-}{[CdCl^+] f_+}$

$$\log K = \log \frac{[Cd^{++}] \times [Cl^-]}{[CdCl^+]} - \frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} + B'\mu$$

By plotting $\log \frac{[Cd^{++}] \times [Cl^-]}{[CdCl^+]} - \frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}}$ against μ

we get a value of $\log K$ and so K.

Temperature (°C)	15	25	35	45
$K \times 10^3$	11.0	10.7	10.0	8.7

Hence values of K of Davies, Monk, Evans and Nancollas for the sulphates of divalent metals have to be revised. This is being done in our laboratory.

It may be pointed out that the value of B given as $AZ^2 \times 0.2$ by Davies in the equation $-\log f = \frac{AZ^2 \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - B\mu$ does not seem to be correct, because the slope in case of $CdCl^+$ dealt with earlier is different from that calculated by Davies equation. However even when Davies equation is used the values of K are not materially changed.

We are also determining the dissociation constant of alums by a combination of a number of cells and the conclusion which we have tentatively arrived are slightly different from results obtained so far.

The e.m.f. method with liquid junction potential has also been used for studying the dissociation of $M(SCN)^+$ at 35° . The authors have used the empirical relation of Davies¹¹

$$-\log f = AZ^2 \left(\frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - 0.2 \mu \right)$$

for the calculation of the activity coefficient of ions concerned. Dissociation constant of the $MSCN^{+3}$ for the salts of some divalent metal, at 35° is given below :

$MSCN^+$	Cd	Zn	Mn	Co	Ni
$K \times 10^3$	8.4	38.3	27.1	17.1	14.0

In these cells l.j.p. has not been eliminated. We intend to eliminate l.j.p. by using suitable cells.

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